

Recommendation System for BSNL Network in SSA Srinagar

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ABSTRACT- Recommender is a Web service that recommends users using their browsing patterns for the type of material they prefer. It tries to forecast a user's preferences or ratings for an item. It leverages the web mining idea, which includes a collection of data mining techniques employed to gather usable knowledge and implicit information from web data. My research is built on a system of collaborative advice. It delivers better result than content filter algorithm. I use a collaborative filtering algorithm. I propose a BSNL telecom network recommendation system based on a variety of collaborative algorithms applied for BSNL networking sites' complicated data set. Experiments are carried out to examine the varying effects of various algorithms on a dataset supplied from BSNL at SSA Srinagar BTS locations on recommended system performance and accuracy. I have identified the high traffic locations and the channel traffic rate. I evaluate SDCCH block calls sites, cell use, SDCCH dropping percentage, total site calls, TCH drop, total cell derivatives. During the analysis of this data set of BSNL telecommunications websites, I found the losing sites, the biggest income sites and those typically downloaded sites (non-working sites).

KEYWORDS- Recommendation System, Anaconda Navigator, SDCCH, TCH, Handover, GSM, CCR.

I. INTRODUCTION

Every client faces several alternatives in today's environment. There's a vast variety of choices for reading a book without any clear insight of what I want in my quest. I could spend a lot of time on the internet and travel around different sites to hit gold. I could seek other people's recommendations. But it would be a big assistance if a website or app were presented which could suggest books to me based on what I had read before. I can only log in and voilà, rather than waste time on several websites! Tailored to my taste 10 recommended books. This is what engines advocate, and most companies are already using their power. Google to Goodreads are one of the most popular

machinery learning applications for recommendation systems, ranging from Amazon to Netflix. Others inclined to buy things that their friends or people they trusted suggested them. This was the main way of selling when the goods was in dispute. But once the digital era came, this circle grew to include sites that use a certain type of engine to recommend. An engine for recommendation analyses the data using several algorithms and suggests consumers the most relevant stuff. First it collects a customer's previous behaviour, which makes it possible for users to purchase things. The engine of recommendations operates by doing the following steps:

A. Data Collection

The first and most important stage towards the construction of the recommendation motor. There are two ways to acquire data: explicit and implicit[2].

Explicit data are information deliberately submitted by users, e.g. film ratings.

Implicit data is information which is not deliberately supplied but is collected from data streams accessible such as search history, clicks, order history, etc.

B. Data storage

the data level determines how well the model suggestions can achieve. For example, the more ratings people make films, the better the suggestions for other users in a film recommendation system. The data type plays a crucial role in determining the storage type that must be employed. A normal SQL database may contain this storage[1].

C. Data filtering

we have to filter it to get the important information necessary to build the final guidelines after collection and storage. Different algorithms assist us facilitate the filtration process.

Research and solutions for telecommunications network management focus for many years on automation of operations that maintain complex networks in operational conditions and at the same time making them lucrative for network operators. Given the continually greater magnitude

and complexity of the issue field combined with unique limitations, it is nearly difficult to have a completely automated management method. The NOCs still supervise and manage network operations in order to react to the large numbers of messages, mistakes, warnings and faults continually streaming from a controlled network. the NOC operators have the obligation to control and manage the network. In the past, Network Operators used expert systems or were highly relied on their operational staff's expert knowledge. Taking into account current growth of the size and complexity of the managed telecommunication network, the existing manual and semi-automated procedures are generally recognized and accepted.[3] In this study, we examine the applicability of recommendation systems as a way of helping NOC operators react properly to issues in the network that they manage.

I seek to investigate to what degree it is feasible, using implicit feedback and advanced recommendation algorithms, to profile the clients. I used a BSNL Telecommunications Operator data set. I used it. With this data set I used pre-process approaches to understand the feasibility and examined numerous algorithms. The results reveal that, when we have historical data on prior customer adherence, our methodology is capable of inferring the best product or service to announce customers, suggesting that the algorithms may enhance suggestions inside a telecommunication provider.

II. OBJECTIVES

- Figure out which of the sites are important, which of the sites provide highest revenue. Sites which are usually down (non- working sites).
- Figure out which of the sites have faulty hardware.
- Determine the traffic sites and traffic rate per channel.
- Determine sites with SDCCH block calls, Cell utilization, SDCCH drop percentage, Total calls in site, TCH drop, Total cell derivatives and Reverse generating sites.

III. SOFTWARE/LIBRARIES USED

- Python Language
- Mat Plot lib.
- Pandas
- Anaconda
- MS-Excel
- Jupyter Notebook.

IV. PARAMETERS TO STUDY

Some of the parameters that i studied and analysed in the whole project:

A. Traffic (Erlang):

The volume of data travelling over the network at a particular point in time is network traffic or data traffic. Network data is usually contained in network packets that supply network loading.[4] Traffic is measured in units of

Erlang hours by means of the measurement of total labour, generally in excess of 24 hours, per resource or facility. It also covers the interaction between traffic-sensitive devices and the rate at which calls are made. It is the product of the average intensity of traffic and the research time period.

V. TRAFFIC VOLUME = TRAFFIC INTENSITY* TIME

The traffic industry has three main sub-sectors: telecommunications (the biggest), telecommunications (the second largest) and wireless communications. The main function is distance communication. It offers a technological basis for corporate communications and the wide variety of IT.

THE MAYER Channel of Traffic: Channel of Transportation (TCH) is utilised for transportation of speech and data. A 26 frame multi frame or collection of 26 TDMA frames is used to create traffic channels. A multi-frame 26 frame length is 120ms. Of the 26 frames, 24 are utilised for traffic, 1 is utilised for the sluggish control channel linked with this.

A. Channel signals

The air interface signalling channels are used for call setup, paging, call maintenance, and sync, etc. There are three kinds of signals: Broadcast, Common Control and Dedicated Channels.[6]

B. SDCCH Channel

SDCCH is used to exchange communication signals between the mobile GSM and network (base station). That is used to establish a traffic connection for pure signalling purposes. The RACH base station sent by the mobile station is allotted to the SDCCH response from AGCH.

C. SDCCH Call Drop

The SDCCH Call Drop Rate specifies a call drop chance while the SDCCH occupies the MS. One of the accessibilities KPIs is the Call drop rate of SDCCH. The KPI shows signalling channels' seizure status. If the value of this KPI is high, it will severely effect user experience.[7]

SDCCH call fall rate = (SDCCH Call drops + successful channel transfer SDCCH seizure) SDCCH call drop rate

D. TCH drop rate of 100%

TCH drop (or drop-down call) can be widely categorised into three subclasses:

- A. Link degradation (uplink and downlink) either deterioration of the signal force which fails at or below the sensitivity of the base station (about -110 dBm) or the sensitivity of the mobile station (about -104 dBm) or, typically because of interference, deterioration of linking quality.
- B. Excess TA (TA>63 or high TA excess trajectory imbalance. The rate of drop-off from SDDCH: The SDCCH rate of call drop shows the likelihood of call drop while the MS occupies the SDCCH. SDCCH's accessibility KPI call drop rate one. The KPI represents the signalling channel seizure.

Call Setup Success Rate

The Call Setup Success Rate (CSSR) is the proportion of a call which makes a link to the numbers (due to various reasons not all call attempts end with a connection to the dialled number).

E. Handover

Handover is a control mechanism started when mobile devices migrate from their current cell to the nearby cell. A mobile phone user is always moving. In such a case, especially if the user is using the phone, the mobile connection should also be maintained. These connection transfer from one cell to another should be rapid and so users do not know that a transfer has occurred.

F. Drop Calls

The dropped rate is the percent of the telephone call that was stopped before the speakers ended their conversation tone for technical reasons and before one of them stopped (dropped call). Usually, this fraction is measured in a proportion of calls. A call attempt calls a call setup process that results in a connected call if successful. A related call may be discontinued because of a technical reason prior to the calling parties, which means telephone conversations before either of the parties has stopped. These calls are categorised as dropped calls.

G. Busy hours

Busy hour as the peak of one hour on the day when the highest number of subscriber traffic is handled by leading outsourcing businesses (CPU, memory use, IOPS). The average intensity of traffic for this timeframe remains unbroken for 60 minutes. The busiest day in typical week is supposed to be, with the exception of holidays, weekends and events.[8]. The 60 minutes serve as a means by continuously supporting ChatBot technological deployments of other AI-based services to improve digital images by providing online reputation management.

VI. SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

A. Data Munging

In order to make it more relevant and useful for many downstream applications such as analytics, Data Munging is the act of converging data from a "raw" form into another one. This may involve more munging, data visualisation, data aggregation, statistical model training and many more possible applications. The process of data munging normally follows a number of broad processes, starting with obtaining the data in a raw form from the data source, "ganging" crude data into algorithms and parsing data into predetermined data structures.

Data munging is the first step by which raw data is better adapted to downstream systems and consumers in content or format. In the late 60s it was coined as a somewhat negative phrase for activities and changes that degrade a data set gradually and fast became connected to the backronym "Mash Until No Good," or "Mung Until No Good," which were repeatedly described. "Mung"

However, as data practitioners' diversity, experience and specialty developed in the Internet age, 'munging' and 'disturbing' became general words that were similarly used to "code" software developers.

These phrases have grown further, and currently apply especially to the early collecting, preparation and refining of raw data, with the increase in cloud computing's, storage and increasingly advanced analytics.[2]

The many verticals, case storages, user kinds and systems that employ company data might take on countless shapes with the peculiarities of munging.

- **Data scanning:** Munging generally starts with data scanning. The search for new associations in existing data analysing data (EDA) in an analyst' s analysis is always starting with a degree of data discernment if he looks just at new information in the first data analysis (IDA).
- **Data transformation:** Once the content and structure of the raw data has been determined, it must be translated into new, downstream forms. This stage includes pure data rearrangement, such as unsettling hierarchical JSON data, the DE standardization of different tables in order to obtain important information from a single location or the reshaping and aggregation of time series data in the dimension and scope of interest.
- **Enhanced data:** optionally, data Mungers can choose to execute extra enrichment procedures once data are ready for consumption. This entails the search for other information sources to broaden the scope or substance of current data.
- **Validation of data:** Validation is the final, maybe the most crucial, phase. The data is now ready to be used, but certain common sense or health checks are required if the data processed are to be trusted. This stage enables users to find typos, wrong mappings, transformation difficulties and even uncommon corruption caused by computer failure or errors[5].

Python data munging: In the fields of actual data munging tools and software, data engineers, analysts and scientists have access to a number of solutions. Generic programmes such as Excel and Tableau – from searches of types to the use of pivoted tables to occasional information viewing and simple macro – can conduct the most basic munging activities. But a more flexible, strong programming language is far more useful for frequent mungers and wranglers. In terms of data stroke, Python is typically acclaimed as the most versatile, common programming language. With one of third-party library sets in particular extensive data processing and analytics tools, such as Pandas, NumPy and SciPy. Much complicated data munging work is simplified by Python. In particular Pandas is one of the most rapidly developing and most supported data munging library, but being being a small fraction of the huge Python ecosystem. Thanks to simplicity, more intuitive formatting and a concentration on readable English-speaking adjacent grammar, Python is also easier to learn than many others. Thanks to Python's extensive applicability, wealthy libraries and online assistance, new

practitioners will find the language beneficial, from Web construction to Workflow automation, well beyond examples of data processing.

We use BSNL Telecommunications dataset Jan 2G Ericsson. The data package we use is raw data and we need to mung our data so that our data package may be adapted for various techniques:.

- Anaconda Navigator: A GUI based navigation programmed is included with Anaconda, making developer life easier. The Spyder IDE and the Jupyter notebook are included as preloaded projects. This enables you to rapidly start a project on your GUI desktop. In order to start work from our newly-established navigation environment, we have to choose our environment from the left toolbar. I must next install the tools we want to utilize.
- It's a jupyter notebook for myself, in particular. I perform the most of my data science work there, and this for me is a productive and efficient Python IDE. Click on the Install button on the Jupyter notebook dock tile. The remainder is going to be done by Navigator.
- The Jupyter Notebook is an open-source web tool for the creation and sharing of documents containing live code, equations, images and narrative texts. The applications include: data purification and transformation, numerical simulation, statistical modelling, display of data, machine learning etc.[4]
- Jupyter Notebook offers a user-friendly, interactive data scientific environment across several computer languages which works as a presentation and/or educational tool not simply as an IDE. For those that are just beginning with data science, it is great. Without network connectivity, you can even run Jupyter.
- Case Study using Python: I worked on the one-month data provided by the BSNL Telecom Srinagar which I loaded in the Excel sheet, and represented it in the form of graphs so that we get the desirable information. This dataset consists of 11564 rows and 36columns.
- Information such as Cell Peak hour, TCH Traffic, SDCCH Block calls etc., of 359 sites in Srinagar.
- First, we'll import our standard libraries and read the dataset in Python.

I used PANDAS library and imported it by using the command "import pandas as pd".

Import the BSNL dataset into Python and analyzing it:

Analyzing our Jan 2g BSNL data set after importing it to python. By using the commands:

```
df=pd.read_excel(path)
df.shape \\Total number of rows and
columns before data munging=1156,36
```

```
df.head \\Displays initial rows.
```

```
df= df[1:] \\By applying this command of data set
the first 13 rows are deleted from the data frame(df) and it
displays rows 13 onwards and save in our data frame.
```

Make a header:

```
Header =df.iloc[0]
```

Now, 'n' has to make header.

```
df.columns = header,then Run
df.column(shows header in afile)
```

We have to delete some columns which are of no use tous.

```
df=df.drop [ df [ "cell name"]
```

```
df.shape(11550,25)
```

Removing an unexpected value in rows and columns

```
Df=df.dropna(thresh=10)
```

```
Df=df.drop[df[df["cell name"]=="SNMICRC"].index
```

```
Df.shape(11519,25)
```

Deleting duplicate data that is repeated in the middle of the dataset.

```
df=df.drop_duplicates()
```

Deleting the dummy data in dataframe.

```
df=df.drop(.index[359])
```

Save it to dataframe

```
df.shape(11129,25)
```

Number of rows and columns after deleting the dummy data.

Grouping of the similar data.

```
rf=df.groupby('CELLNAME')
```

VII. RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

A. Objectives:

- Sites in which voice traffic is more.
- Sites which are idol for a longtime.
- Sites with network problems.
- Sites with hardware problems.
- Sites with high data consumption.
- Sites with less data consumption i.e, sites where no data is used at all.
- Sites which generates maximum revenue.
- Sites at which hardware should be increased.
- RESULT 1: Will give you the largest revenue generating sites from the whole dataset as shown in Figure 1
- RESULT 2: 10 Largest revenue generating sites which can be seen in Figure 2.
- RESULT 3: 5 Largest Sites with highest SDCCH Blockin3 .This can be illustrated in figure .
- RESULT 4: The graph shows sites with highest TCH Call Drop Rate as shown in Figure 4. TCH Call Drop is related to retainability. It indicates the probability of call drops due to various reasons like hardware issue or handover issues.
- RESULT 5: (HOSR) is the ratio of the number of successful handovers to the handover request as illustrated in Figure 5. The major purpose of handover is to guarantee call continuity, improve speech quality, reduce cross interference in the network and thus provide better services for mobile station subscribers.

Figure 1: A successful handover

Figure 3: Largest Sites with highest SDCCH Blocking

Figure 2: Call Continuity handover

Figure 4: The graph shows sites with highest TCH Call Drop Rate

ID	Count 1	Count 2	Cell Name	Date	Location	Region	Success Rate 1	Success Rate 2
8924	10358	SFDHMT	2020-01-28	SHARIFABADHMT	Jammu & Kashmir	28	23	
10886	4831	ZNKTERB	2020-01-13	ZAIKOTEXCHO	Jammu & Kashmir	28	23	
1345	4519	BHNAEXB	2020-01-13	BEMNAEXCHANGE	Jammu & Kashmir	28	23	
4482	6858	JOLHRA	2020-01-19	JOLILANOR	Jammu & Kashmir	28	23	
666	5616	ARPTWA	2020-01-18	AIRPORT_NEW	Jammu & Kashmir	28	23	
1346	4892	BHNAEXB	2020-01-14	BEMNAEXCHANGE	Jammu & Kashmir	28	23	
8921	9239	SFDHMT	2020-01-26	SHARIFABADHMT	Jammu & Kashmir	28	23	
1338	2281	BHNAEXB	2020-01-07	BEMNAEXCHANGE	Jammu & Kashmir	28	23	

10 rows × 25 columns

Figure 5: (HOSR) is the ratio of the number of successful handovers to the handover request

VIII. RESULTS GENERATED BY CLUSTERING

Steps for K-means clustering algorithm:

- First, import all the required libraries.
- Read the CSV file.
- We will be taking different variables from the data for generating various results“TCH Drop(%), TCH Traffic (Erlang) as shown in figure 6 , SDCCH Success Calls(CMSESTAB) as shown in Figure 7, SDCCH Blocking as illustrated in Figure 8 , TCH Success Calls(TMSESTB), TCH Dropped Connections(TNDROP)” as shown in Figure 9.
- We will be taking these variables and visualizing the data points between them.
- In this step, we have to choose the number of clusters (k) and we have to select random centroids for each cluster. We will pick 3 clusters and then elect random observations from the data as the centroids.
- Red dot represents the 3 centroid for each cluster.
- Our plots are generated with 3 clusters represented by 3 colors (blue, green, cyan)
- and 3 centroids (red dots).

Figure 6: TCH Drop (%) and TCH Traffic (Erlang)

Figure 7: TCH Drop (%) and SDCCH Succ Calls

Figure 8: SDCCH Blocking VS SDCCH Calls

Figure 9: TCH Calls VS TCH Dropped Calls

IX. CONCLUSION

In helping users to identify and obtain mobile applications of interest, a recommender system was built. The system is a prototype based on a study of previous research and related systems. It shows the potential of application recommendations and identifies the challenges present in the domain, it also provides recommended applications from a user’s first launch of the system by utilizing the user’s location. Preliminary evaluations were performed. For making the recommender system we used the tools like software viz python including Mat Plot Lib, panda libraries. We used excel data in the form of diagrammatic form so that data can be easily read. In this designing, we figure out which of the sites are important, which of the sites provide highest revenue and the sites which are usually down (non-working sites).We also figure out which of the sites are hardware faulty or which are not. We determined the traffic sites and traffic rate per channel. We also determined sites with SDCCH block calls, cell utilization, SDCCH drop percentage, total calls in site, TCH drop, total cell derivatives and reverse generating sites.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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